

Treatment of Nasal Congestion and Prevention of *Rhinitis Medicamentosa*

Domina Petric, MD (Clinical pharmacology and toxicology, UHC Split, Croatia)

ABSTRACT

Nasal congestion is one of the leading symptoms of rhinitis and rhinosinusitis. Excessive use of nasal decongestant sprays can cause rebound congestion and *rhinitis medicamentosa*. In order to prevent the rebound congestion use of topical and systemic decongestants should be restricted to no more than five days; moisturizing nasal ointments, gels or sprays should be administered simultaneously with decongestant agent; hypertonic saline should be used instead of decongestant agent in the case of mild nasal congestion, as well as humidifiers and vaporizers; intranasal glucocorticoid should be administered in the case of allergic rhinitis.

INTRODUCTION

Nasal congestion (stiffness) is one of the leading symptoms of rhinitis and rhinosinusitis. Other symptoms are sneezing, rhinorrhea (anterior and/or posterior), nasal itching and cough. Nasal decongestant sprays can cause *rhinitis medicamentosa*. Regular use of over-the-counter (OTC) decongestant nasal sprays is the cause of rebound nasal congestion because of which patient administers nasal decongestant spray more frequently. The more frequently patient administers nasal decongestant, the more severe is the rebound nasal congestion (*circulus vitiosus*). The risk of developing *rhinitis medicamentosa* can be minimized by limiting use of nasal decongestant sprays to a maximum of five days and not exceeding recommended frequencies. Rhinitis medicamentosa is less likely to occur if the patient is administering and intranasal glucocorticoid along with the nasal decongestant¹.

NASAL CONGESTION

Nasal congestion or obstruction is one of the most frequent symptoms encountered in primary care and specialist clinics, and it is often the predominant symptom in upper respiratory tract disorders, such as allergic rhinitis, rhinosinusitis, nonallergic rhinitis, and nasal polyposis. Additionally, nasal congestion is also a common symptom in otitis media and asthma, and it can contribute to the onset or worsening of sleep disturbances, including obstructive sleep apnea². The pathophysiology of nasal congestion includes mucosal inflammation, which is the central pathophysiological mechanism, often involving increased venous engorgement, increased nasal secretions, and tissue swelling/edema; physical problems affecting the structure of the nasal passage; and/or modulation of sensory perception^{3,4}.

Inflammation associated with allergic rhinitis and rhinosinusitis can reduce the physical

size of the nasal passages by inducing vasodilatation, increasing blood flow and increasing vascular permeability. The result is engorgement of nasal venous sinusoids, swelling of the anterior and inferior turbinates and obstruction of nasal airflow, ultimately contributing to nasal congestion⁵.

NASAL DECONGESTANTS

Systemic and topical nasal decongestants are recommended for the symptomatic treatment of nasal congestion during acute nasopharyngeal diseases. The vasoconstrictors (decongestants) are usually sympathomimetic amines or chemically related imidazoles. The α -adrenergic agonists constrict subepithelial precapillary sphincter, arterioles and venous sinuses, whilst the β -agonists mediate vasodilatation. Prolonged pharmacological vasoconstriction is probably followed by vasodilatation, and ultimately the muscle responds less well to any repeated nasal application of the vasoconstrictors. The most commonly used sympathomimetic decongestants are ephedrine and phenylephrine. The common imidazole vasoconstrictors are xylometazoline, oxymetazoline and naphazoline. Relief from nasal obstruction is often immediate, but commonly followed by reactive nasal congestion. Once the nasal block develops again, the troubled patient returns to the decongestant⁶.

Systemic decongestants are usually combined with paracetamol or ibuprofen to provide relief of both nasal congestion symptoms and systemic symptoms of common cold or flu, such as fever and muscle pain. Although not directly applied on nasal mucosa, systemic decongestants also cause nasal vasoconstriction and thus, may lead to rebound congestion with prolonged use.

REBOUND CONGESTION

Rebound congestion can be defined as deterioration of the feeling of nasal congestion, for which topical nasal decongestants were initially prescribed, that occurs during repeated use of decongestants or after stopping this treatment^{7,8}.

There are two pharmaco-biological hypotheses for rebound congestion.

Hypothesis 1. Rebound effect may be due to ischaemia of the nasal mucosa. Stimulation of α_2 -receptors induces intense vasoconstriction of submucosal arterioles⁹. This ischaemia would predispose to the development of interstitial edema^{10,11}.

Hypothesis 2. The number of mucosal α -adrenergic receptors would be decreased by downregulation. Endogenous noradrenaline production would be decreased by presynaptic negative feedback. These effects would induce relative dilatation of the submucosal sinusoid

venous plexuses due to loss of dynamic venous vasoconstriction^{10,12,13}. Adrenergic receptors could also become refractory to nasal decongestants, causing the patient to increase the doses of nasal decongestants. This is due to tachyphylaxis^{9,14}.

RHINITIS MEDICAMENTOSA

Rhinitis medicamentosa may be described as persistent rhinitis induced by prolonged use of topical nasal decongestants: sympathomimetic amines and imidazoles¹⁴. *Rhinitis medicamentosa* usually occurs following an episode of acute viral rhinitis and is characterized by persistent nasal congestion, usually isolated, and occurring increasingly rapidly after application of nasal decongestants¹³. This congestion causes the patient to increase the frequency of application and the quantity applied, resulting in dependence on topical nasal decongestants¹⁰.

MOISTURIZING NASAL OINTMENTS, GELS AND SPRAYS

Moisturizing nasal ointments, gels and sprays containing isotonic seawater (sodium chloride), dexpanthenol, vitamin A and/or vitamin E may be useful for the additional treatment of nasal congestion and prevention or treatment of rebound nasal congestion.

Dexpanthenol is the alcoholic analogue of pantothenic acid, and it is oxidized to this

substance within the tissues. Studies have shown that dexpanthenol spray promotes cell proliferation and protects the nasal epithelium¹⁵. The combination of dexpanthenol with nasal decongestants significantly decreases the toxic effects of decongestants with regard to cilia function and cell growth¹⁶.

PREVENTION OF *RHINITIS MEDICAMENTOSA*

First, topical or systemic nasal decongestants should not be used for more than 5 days. Medical doctors and pharmacists must educate patients about this fact.

Second, hypertonic saline has a weak anti-edema action and can be used instead of decongestants in the case of mild nasal congestion.

Third, doctors and pharmacists can advise patients to use moisturizing nasal ointments, gels or sprays simultaneously during the decongestants-based therapy or to use products that already contain a combination of both moisturizing agent and decongestant agent.

Fourth, use of humidifier or vaporizer may relieve symptoms of nasal congestion and reduce the need for nasal decongestants.

Fifth, patients should be educated to visit their family doctor/general practitioner if the symptoms of nasal congestion persist more than 3 days, especially if fever is also present. In these

cases, antibiotic therapy may be indicated.

If the diagnosis of allergic rhinitis is suspected, intranasal corticosteroid should be prescribed. In the case of nasal polyps, surgical treatment may be indicated.

CONCLUSION

Nasal congestion is a very common symptom. Nasal decongestants are widely available as OTC drugs. Many patients do not visit their family doctor/general practitioner in the case of prolonged nasal congestion, but just keep going on with nasal decongestant therapy on their own instead. Prolonged use of decongestants may lead to rebound congestion and *rhinitis medicamentosa*. Use of topical and systemic decongestants should be restricted to no more than five days. Moisturizing nasal ointments, gels or sprays should be used simultaneously with decongestant agent. Hypertonic saline should be used in the case of mild nasal congestion. Use of humidifiers and vaporizers may also relieve symptoms of nasal congestion. Patients must be educated to seek medical advice if nasal congestion persists for more than three days. *Rhinitis medicamentosa* is also less likely to occur if the patient is administering and intranasal glucocorticoid along with the nasal decongestant. In the case of nasal polyps, surgical treatment may be indicated.

REFERENCES

1. Peden D. An overview of rhinitis. Corren J, Feldweg AM, ed. UpToDate. Waltham, MA: UpToDate Inc. <https://www.uptodate.com> (Accessed on September 14, 2021.)
2. Corey JP, Houser SM, Ng BA. Nasal congestion: a review of its etiology, evaluation, and treatment. *Ear Nose Throat J.* 2000;79(9):690–698.
3. Naclerio RM, Bachert C, Baraniuk JN. Pathophysiology of nasal congestion. *Int J Gen Med.* 2010;3:47-57.
4. Proud D, Naclerio RM, Gwaltney JM, Hendley JO. Kinins are generated in nasal secretions during natural rhinovirus colds. *J Infect Dis.* 1990;161(1):120–123.
5. Corboz MR, Mutter JC, Rivelli MA, et al. Alpha2-adrenoceptor agonists as nasal decongestants. *Pulm Pharmacol Ther.* 2007;20(2):149–156.
6. Capel LH, Swanston AR. Beware congesting nasal decongestants. *Br Med J.* 1986;293(6557):1258-1259.
7. Costantino G, Ceriani E, Sandrone G, et al. Ischemic stroke in a man with naphazoline abuse. *Am J Emerg Med* 2007;25:983.
8. Claudet I, Fries F. Danger des vasoconstricteurs chez le nourrisson, à propos d'une observation. *Arch Pediatr.* 1997;4:538-41.
9. Passali D, Salemi L, Passali GC, et al. Nasal decongestants in the treatment of chronic nasal obstruction: efficacy and safety of use. *Expert Opin Drug Saf.* 2006;5:783-90.
10. Graf P. Rhinitis medicamentosa: a review of causes and treatment. *Treat Respir Med.* 2005;4:21-9.
11. Graf PM, Hallen H. Changes in nasal reactivity in patients with rhinitis medicamentosa after treatment with fluticasone propionate and placebo nasal spray. *ORL J Otorhinolaryngol Relat Spec.* 1998;60:334-8.
12. Hein P, Martin MC. Signal transduction and regulation: are all alpha1-adrenergic receptor subtypes created equal? *Biochem Pharmacol.* 2007;73:1097-106.

13. Ramey JT, Bailen E, Lockey RF. Rhinitis medicamentosa. *J Investig Allergol Clin Immunol*. 2006;16:148-55.
14. Akerlund A, Bende M. Sustained use of xylometazoline nose drops aggravates vasomotor rhinitis. *Am J Rhinol*. 1991;5:157-60.
15. Mösges R, Shah-Hosseini K, Hücke H-P, Joisten M-J. Dexpantenol: An Overview of its Contribution to Symptom Relief in Acute Rhinitis Treated with Decongestant Nasal Sprays. *Advances in Therapy*. 2017;34(8):1850-1858.
16. Klöcker N, Rudolph P, Verse T. Evaluation of protective and therapeutic effects of dexpantenol on nasal decongestants and preservatives: results of cytotoxic studies in vitro. *Am J Rhinol*. 2004;18(5):315–320.